

A Study of Burnout in Relation to Professional Commitment of College Teachers in Himachal Pradesh

Pardeep Singh Dehal

Assistant Professor

Deptt. of Education, ICDEOL, HPU, Shimla

Received : 15/01/2023

1st BPR : 26/01/2023

2nd BPR : 11/02/2023

Accepted : 26/02/2023

Abstract

Teaching has been one of the oldest and most respected professions in the world. The task of teacher is shaping the future of citizens and thereby society and nation. Due to respectful duty, teacher has been respectful in all society through ancient to Buddhist period. In the modern period teacher is regarded as a custodian and architect of a nation. Today, there are many duties and responsibilities of a teachers working at different level of education. Burnout is the outcome of excessive stress. Many illnesses like liver and heart disease are likely due to psychological stresses of modern life. The percentage of burnout is likely higher today. Better understanding of this stress outcome has to be promoted. The study was delimited to the thirty four governments and private degree Colleges located in territory of Himachal Pradesh and seven districts i.e. Hamirpur, Bilaspur, Una, Kangra, Shimla Chamba and Mandi of Himachal Pradesh. The investigator in the present study has adopted descriptive survey method. The population for the present study comprised teachers teaching degree classes in government and private (aided and non-aided) colleges affiliated to Himachal Pradesh University. Since, it was not possible to cover all the colleges in the State of Himachal Pradesh, stratified random sampling technique was applied, first for selection of colleges by giving due weightage to type of management, mode of appointment, location and gender and secondly to draw the sample of 546 teachers from the colleges. In the present study, the researcher used the following tools for collection of data: Burnout Inventory (BI) developed by Karuna Shankar Misra (2005). Means, S.Ds. and t-value as well as analysis of variance (ANOVA) used as a statistical techniques to analyse and interpret the data used as a statistical techniques to analyse and interpret the data.

Key words : Burnout, Commitment, College Teacher.

Introduction:

The job of a teacher is to teach the disciples to develop insight and reasoning that can be used to live a life. There is no doubt that profession of teaching is very large, deep and needs visionary actions. Teachers are often expected to correct social evils or problems while educating the students in academic and skill areas, providing enrichment activities, meeting the individual needs of students and encouraging student's moral and ethical development. Teachers have found their credibility eroding with large community.

The Maslach Burnout inventory was used by Worley et al. (2008) for studying the three factors namely emotional exhaustion, personal accomplishment and depersonalization of an individual. However, Mishra (2005) used non-accomplishment, depersonalization, emotional exhaustion, friction, task avoidance, distancing neglecting and easy going approach as the indicators of burnout among teachers. Depending on the particular case, burnout may be alleviated by changes in the work environment and job demands, as well as changes in the individual's behaviour and approach to work. If nothing changes, however, burnout tends to create a downward spiral, in which an unsustainable situation leads to exhaustion and dissatisfaction, which leads to poor performance, which in turn leads to a worsened work situation or even job loss and increased stress on the

individual. The term commitment means a pledge, promise and duty towards something. Professional commitment means commitment to a profession. Therefore, professional commitment is a person's pledge, promise, or resolution toward his/her profession.

Various definitions of professional commitment are given by several educators and researchers. Teachers are considered builder and maker of the society. Teachers should be committed to their profession. The quality of teaching depends a great deal on the level of teacher's involvement in relation to the professional commitment. . It is the total involvement of a teacher that gives a shining outlook to this profession and makes it impressive and interesting. He is a creative person involved in innovative activities and research work. Teacher's love for research and his experience in research are vital for the growth of an institution and also for his commitment towards the profession.

Objective of the study: To study burnout in relation to professional commitment of college teachers in Himachal Pradesh.

Hypothesis of the study:

There is no significant difference among different level of professional commitment of college teachers in Himachal Pradesh on burn out.

Methodology of the study:

This chapter deals with description of method and procedure adopted to complete the present study. The plan and procedure is a blue print of a research study. Without planning, a researcher cannot achieve objectives with good reliability and validity. Therefore, method and procedure of any research is essential for quality information and thereby quality findings. The investigator in the present study has adopted descriptive survey method.

The descriptive method involves quantitative information that can be tabulated along a continuum in numerical form. It involves gathering data that describe events and then organizes, tabulates, depicts, and describes the data collection (Glass & Hopkins, 1984). Descriptive research summarized many information in form of mean, median, mode, standard deviation, variance, percentage, correlation between variables etc. The descriptive research often uses quasi-experimental research design (Campbell & Stanley, 1963). Data collection in descriptive research includes surveys, interviews, observations, and portfolios. The descriptive research involves the description, recording, analysis and interpretation of conditions that exist. It involves some types of comparison or contrast and attempts to discover relationships between existing non-manipulated variables (Best, 1981).

Population and Sample of the Study:

Population is the entire aggregation of cases or units that meet criteria set by investigator. According to Best (2007), "A population is any group of individuals who have one or more characteristics in common that are of interest to the researcher. The population for the present study comprised teachers teaching degree classes in government and private (aided and non-aided) colleges affiliated to Himachal Pradesh University. Since, it was not possible to cover all the colleges in the State of Himachal Pradesh, stratified random sampling technique was applied, first for selection of colleges by giving due weightage to type of management, mode of appointment, location and gender and secondly to draw the sample of 546 teachers from the colleges.

Tools and Techniques used: A researcher requires many data-gathering tools or techniques. Tools are essential for measurement of traits of variables and it they guide the researcher in data collection and also in evaluation. In the present study, the researcher used the following tools for collection of data:

Burnout Inventory (BI) developed by Karuna Shankar Misra (2005).

Professional Commitment Scale (PCS) constructed and standardized by the investigator is also used to collect the data.

The Burnout Inventory used in the present study was originally developed by Karuna Shankar Mirsa to measure burnout among teachers working in higher education. The BI contains 48 items and it

measures burnout in terms of eight dimensions namely Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization and Non-accomplishment, Friction, Task avoidance, Distancing, Neglecting and Easy going. Descriptive statistics like mean, S.D., skewness and kurtosis were calculated to see normality and other purposes. To find out difference between two groups t-test was used. To find out differences among different levels of professional commitment on burnout of college teachers analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used.

Analysis and interpretation of the data:

After data collection and analysis of data, main work of researcher is to present results and interpretation in systematic and effective way.

Burnout in Relation to Professional Commitment of College Teachers in Himachal Pradesh

To find out differences among different levels of professional commitment on burnout of college teachers analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. Mean and standard deviation of different level of professional commitment on burnout of college teachers are given in Table1. Summary of one way analysis of variance is given in Table2. Means and standard deviations of college teachers with low, average and high professional commitment on total burnout and its dimensions are presented in Figure given below.

Figure-1: Showing means and S.Ds. of college teachers with low, average and high professional commitment on all dimensions of burnout

Figure shows that on non-accomplishment (NA) dimension of burnout mean of college teachers with low professional commitment is higher than average and high professional commitment, while no major mean difference depicted teachers with average and high professional commitment. On depersonalization (Dp) dimension of teachers with low and high professional commitment higher and similar than teachers with average professional commitment. On emotional exhaustion (EE) mean of teachers with low professional commitment is higher than teachers with average and high professional commitment. But teachers with higher professional commitment are higher on emotional exhaustion than teachers with average professional commitment. On friction (F), avoidance (TA), distancing (D), neglecting (N) and easy going (EG) mean of teachers with low professional commitment is higher than teachers with average and high professional commitment. But teachers

with higher professional commitment are higher on these dimensions than teachers with average professional commitment.

Figure-2 also shows that mean of teachers with low professional commitment is higher than teachers with average and high professional commitment on total burnout. But teachers with higher professional commitment are higher than teachers with average professional commitment on total burnout.

Figure-2: Showing means and S.Ds. of college teachers with low, average and high professional commitment on total burnout

Table-1

Mean and standard deviation for college teachers with low, average and high professional commitment on total burnout and its dimensions

Burnout	Professional Commitment								
	Lower			Average			High		
	N	Mean	S.D.	N	Mean	S.D.	N	Mean	S.D.
NA	113	15.027	5.581	250	13.152	4.836	183	13.377	6.420
Dp	113	15.319	4.879	250	13.232	5.179	183	15.333	5.753
EE	113	14.903	5.415	250	13.052	4.548	183	14.262	5.885
F	113	14.062	5.217	250	11.448	4.947	183	12.929	5.838
TA	113	14.752	5.123	250	12.536	4.577	183	13.639	5.742
D	113	14.664	5.022	250	12.416	5.026	183	14.350	5.855
N	113	14.496	5.254	250	12.620	5.459	183	13.574	6.022
EG	113	14.558	4.796	250	12.936	4.900	183	13.617	5.571
Total Burnout	113	117.779	35.965	250	101.392	32.996	183	111.082	41.886

Table-2

Summary of analysis of variance for difference among different level of professional commitment on total burnout and its dimensions of college teachers

Variable	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Sum of Square	F	Probability
Non-Accomplishment	Between	289.103	2	144.551	4.668	.010*
	Within	16814.128	543	30.965		
	Total	17103.231	545	31.382		
Depersonalization	Between	595.264	2	297.632	10.516	.000*
	Within	15367.742	543	28.302		
	Total	15963.005	545	29.290		
Emotional Exhaustion	Between	315.474	2	157.737	5.812	.003*
	Within	14737.663	543	27.141		
	Total	15053.137	545	27.620		
Friction	Between	585.916	2	292.958	10.367	.000*
	Within	15344.467	543	28.259		
	Total	15930.383	545	29.230		
Task Avoidance	Between	403.036	2	201.518	7.730	.000*
	Within	14155.435	543	26.069		
	Total	14558.471	545	26.713		
Distancing	Between	578.456	2	289.228	10.228	.000*
	Within	15355.575	543	28.279		
	Total	15934.031	545	29.237		
Neglecting	Between	290.415	2	145.207	4.607	.010*
	Within	17113.902	543	31.517		
	Total	17404.317	545	31.935		
Easy Going	Between	208.424	2	104.212	3.984	.019*
	Within	14204.076	543	26.159		
	Total	14412.500	545	26.445		
Total Burnout Score	Between	23459.647	2	11729.824	8.663	.000*
	Within	735268.824	543	1354.086		
	Total	758728.471	545	1392.162		
*p<0.05 (Significant at 0.05 level)						

Summary of analysis of variance Table-2 shows that F-values for non-accomplishment, depersonalization, emotional exhaustion, friction, task avoidance, distancing, neglecting, easygoing and total burnout are 4.668, 10.516, 5.812, 10.367, 7.730, 10.228, 4.607, 3.984 and 8.663. Probability of all F-values are lower than 0.05. This means that significant difference exists among teachers with low, average and high professional commitment on total burnout and its dimensions.

Therefore, null hypothesis H_{05} that “There is no significant difference among different level of professional commitment of college teachers in Himachal Pradesh on burn out”, is rejected.

Findings and Conclusion of the Study:

Significant differences were found among college teachers with low, average and high professional commitment on non-accomplishment, depersonalization, emotional exhaustion, friction, task avoidance, distancing, neglecting and easy going dimensions of burnout and total burnout. So we can say that various seminars and workshops should be organized related to overcoming burnout and enhancing the professional commitment of college teachers. Organizer should care that administrators and key persons in government should participate in seminars. College teachers should be given complete academic freedom to work efficiently and attain excellence. For this institution should provide proper facilities.

References:

- Afsar, et. al. (2015). Burnout among secondary school teachers with reference to certain demographic variables. *European Academic Research*, II(11), 14338-14350.
- Ahmad, Q. (1986). Determinants of job involvement among teachers. *Fourth Survey of Research in Education*(1983-88), 1, 917.
- Aggarwal, Y.P. (1997). Perception of burnout and locus of control among college teachers. *Journal of Indian Education*, 23 (3) 17-21
- Al-Kahtani, NS, Allam, Z. (2014). The influence of job burnout, involvement and locus of control on job satisfaction: Some explorations from banking sector in Saudi Arabia. *New York Science Journal*, 7(2), 93-101.
- Al-Kathani Nasser, S. & Allam Safrul (2014). The influence of job burnout, involvement and locus of control on job satisfaction: Some explorations from banking sector in Saudi Arabia. *New York Science Journal*, 7 (2), 93-101.
- Aminabhavi, V. A. & Dharanendriah, A. S. (1997). A study of the factor contributing to job involvement of professional. *Indian Journal of Psychometry and Education*, 28, 109-112.
- Ammabhavi, VLA (1996). Quality of life of professionals in relation to their job involvement and socio-cultural background paper presented in T' Asian and 32" Annual Conference of IAAP, Alirah Muslim University), Aligarh.

